

INTEREST FREE BANKING AS MEANS OF INCLUSIVE FINANCE IN INDIA: THE MALAYSIAN PARADIGM*

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ABSTRACT

Islamic finance, which requires financial activities to be tied closely to economic activities, has gained increasing popularity not only in the Muslim world but also in non-Muslim countries. UK, Singapore, Hong Kong, Germany, China, Japan and Korea are some non-Muslim countries that have had increased interest in Islamic finance. We believe that India, with the third largest Muslim population in the world has high potential to grow the Islamic banking market. This paper examines the experience of Malaysia in developing the Islamic banking market. We scrutinize the strategies pursued by the Malaysian government and the Central Bank in developing the Islamic banking market and complete this with a snapshot data on the growth of the market. After reviewing the current state of Islamic banking in India, we draw lessons from the Malaysian experience that can be applied in India to develop the Islamic banking market.

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1. INTRODUCTION

“In 1936, John Maynard Keynes described the decline of the world’s financial markets as a result of playing at a casino: Short-term speculation with little regard for fundamentals. The same observation could easily be applied to the post-mortem of last year’s global financial crisis.” (Timewell & DiVanna, 2009).

Islamic finance, which requires financial activities to be tied closely to economic activities, has gained increasing popularity not only in the Muslim world but also in non-Muslim countries. According to the Banker’s magazine survey, the size of Shari’ah compliant asset as at 2009 was US\$822 billion, compared to US\$639 billion in 2008 (an increase of 28.6%). The industry has enjoyed a compounded annual growth of 27.86% (2006-2009). Simply put, it’s a fast growing industry and more and more countries are interested in offering Islamic financial services so they are not left out of the bandwagon. Just in 2009, 28 new banks entered into the market. That was a slow year compared to 51 new entrants in 2008 and 78 new entrants in 2007.

Table 1 shows the top 25 countries with Shari’ah compliant assets together with the Muslim population in these countries. The data shows that Iran has the largest Shari’ah compliant asset (36%) followed by Saudi (16%) and Malaysia (11%). Out of the 25 countries only 5 countries, i.e. United Kingdom, Switzerland, Mauritius, Singapore and Thailand, have Muslim population less than 20%, as compared to the total population in the country. All other countries have large Muslim population (70-80%), with Malaysia having slightly more than 50% and Brunei with Muslim population of about 67%.

Simply put, countries with large Muslim population seem to be the main players in the market, however non-Muslim affinitive countries are following suit due to the potential that the industry brings. For example UK, Singapore and Hong Kong have since the 2000s made public its intention to become one of the Islamic financial hubs. These countries have also taken active effort to provide tax neutrality policy change to facilitate Islamic finance offerings. Germany, back in 2004 issued *Sukuk* to tap into the Islamic space. Last year, even France and China have made significant moves to allow Islamic finance operation in their countries. China allowed Bank of Nigxia to establish Islamic window while France has even

attempted to change its legislation¹ to facilitate Islamic finance offerings. Last but not least, Korea has brought some tax policy amendments to the parliament to provide level playing field for *Sukuk* (MOSF, 2009).

If we analyze the size of the Shari'ah compliant asset according to the regions, it seems that GCC countries take the lead with 43% followed by non-GCC MENA countries holding 38% and finally non-MENA countries holding 19% (The Banker, 2009). In the non-MENA region, Malaysia holds about 56.2% share in the region's Shari'ah compliant asset and ranks number 3 in the top 25 list. Malaysia makes a beneficial case study to compare with India due to the progress it has made in the market despite the multi-religion and multi-ethnic composition of the population.

The paper is organized as follows. In section two we will examine the experience of Malaysia in developing the Islamic banking market. We first scrutinize the strategies pursued by the Malaysian government and the Central Bank in developing the Islamic banking market. We also provide snapshot data on the growth of the market. In the third section, we examine the state of Islamic banking in India and conclude the paper with lessons that India can adopt from the Malaysian experience to develop the Islamic banking market.

Table 1: Top 25 countries in the Islamic Finance market as at 2009

Rank	Country	Shari'ah-Compliant Assets \$m ²	%	Muslim Population ³	% Compared To Total Population
1	Iran	293,165.80	35.71%	65,764,991	99.00%
2	Saudi Arabia	127,896.10	15.58%	28,686,633	100%
3	Malaysia	86,488.20	10.54%	13,372,226	52%
4	UAE	84,036.50	10.24%	4,606,551	96%
5	Kuwait	67,630.20	8.24%	2,287,484	85%
6	Bahrain	46,159.40	5.62%	590,961	81.20%
7	Qatar	27,515.40	3.35%	833,285	100%

¹ An amendment the French Civil Code was passed on September 17, 2009 by the French National Assembly but was struck down by the High Court. For further details refer (Timewell & DiVanna, 2009)

² Source: The Banker 2009

³ Source: CIA World Fact Handbook in (Invest East, n.d)

Interest Free Banking As Means of Inclusive Finance In India

8	UK	19,410.50	2.36%	1,650,057	2.70%
9	Turkey	17,827.50	2.17%	76,529,024	99.60%
10	Bangladesh	7,453.30	0.91%	129,522,233	83%
11	Sudan	7,151.10	0.87%	28,761,478	70%
12	Egypt	6,299.70	0.77%	74,774,582	90%
13	Pakistan	5,126.10	0.62%	170,955,661	97%
14	Jordan	4,621.60	0.56%	6,025,801	95%
15	Syria	3,838.80	0.47%	14,932,079	74%
16	Iraq	3,815.00	0.46%	28,077,287	97%
17	Indonesia	3,388.20	0.41%	206,873,780	86.10%
18	Brunei	3,201.40	0.39%	260,087	67%
19	Yemen	1,318.30	0.16%	23,584,555	99%
20	Switzerland	1,040.60	0.13%	235,738	3.1%
21	Mauritius	943.50	0.11%	213,958	16.7%
22	Algeria	837.50	0.10%	33,836,406	99%
23	Tunisia	632.30	0.08%	10,276,612	98%
24	Singapore	618.00	0.08%	791,782	17%
25	Thailand	495.50	0.06%	9,226,757	14%
		820,910.50	100.00%		

2. DEVELOPMENT OF ISLAMIC BANKING MARKET IN MALAYSIA

2.1 Early Progress

The history of Islamic finance in Malaysia dates back to 1969 when the Pilgrims Management Fund Board (“Tabung Haji”) was established as a result of the merger between the Pilgrims Affairs Department and the Malaysian Muslim Pilgrims Savings Corporation. Nonetheless this was a specialized savings institution to help Muslims in Malaysia to save for their pilgrimage. Instead of paying interest to the depositors, Tabung Haji pays dividend based on its investment in equities and other securities.

After the establishment of Tabung Haji, there was continuous demand to set up an Islamic bank in Malaysia. In 1980, the Bumiputra Economic Congress passed a resolution requesting the government to allow Tabung

Haji to establish an Islamic Bank in Malaysia. In line with this resolution, Tabung Haji also formed a study group to explore the possibility of establishing an Islamic bank. On 10th July 1981, the Financial Advisory Board of Tabung Haji and the Study Group agreed that it is imperative to set up a national steering committee to do a comprehensive study on this issue and the Prime Minister should appoint the members of the steering committee (Mohamed Abdullah, 2008).

The government accepted the proposal from Tabung Haji and on 30th July 1981 the National Steering Committee on Islamic Banking was formed. The committee submitted its report on July 5th 1982 proposing the establishment of an Islamic bank with a separate act to govern its operation. The government approved the proposal from the National Steering Committee and in line with this the parliament approved the Islamic Banking Act (IBA) in March 1983 and was effective on the 7th April 1983. IBA not only gave the Central Bank of Malaysia the authority to regulate and supervise Islamic banks but also provided the Islamic banks a universal banking model where they could conduct any banking business as long as it does not contradict Sharī'ah.

All these behind the scene work then gave birth to the first full-fledged Islamic commercial bank in Malaysia, Bank Islam Malaysia, on 1st July 1983. The Government Investment Act (GIA) was also passed in 1983 that allows the government to issue Government Investment Certificates (GIC), a liquid security similar to the Treasury bills, but is Sharī'ah compliant (Bank Negara Malaysia, 1994).

One could benefit from the systematic approach that the Malaysian government and the Central Bank took to develop the Malaysian Islamic banking market which adopts a three phase approach; familiarization, competition and liberalization. Figure 1 depicts the phases in the development plan.

2.2 Phase One - Familiarization

For the first 10 years, there was no competition for Bank Islam as it was the sole provider of Islamic financial services in Malaysia. This allowed the bank to gain experience and be better prepared to compete against the far established conventional bank when the market was opened in the second phase. The Central Bank also pursued a well thought out strategy. It believed that to nurture a successful and comprehensive financial system,

Interest Free Banking As Means of Inclusive Finance In India

be it Islamic or conventional, there are three components that must be in place – large number of players, large number of instruments and establishment of a money market. In the first phase of development, the aim was to increase the number of products offered in the Islamic space because it is easier to experiment, learn and supervise just one Islamic bank at this early stage. At the end of the first phase, i.e. 1992, Bank Islam has developed 21 Islamic banking products (BNM, 1994).

Figure 1 : Implementation of Malaysian Islamic Banking System

Source: Ahmad Mokhtar, et. al, 2007.

The experiment pursued by the Central Bank proved right as Bank Islam demonstrated that it is a viable and competitive banking model. Table 2 shows the growth of the total asset, total deposit and total financing of Bank Islam in its first year of operation (1984) until the end of phase one (1992). In the span of the first 9 years of operation, the total asset of Bank Islam grew by 393% while the total deposit grew by 448%. Total financing grew the highest (524%) to reach RM 1 billion in 1992. This successful growth translated into a profit of RM16.1 million in 1992. The branches of Bank Islam grew almost 8 times compared to the number of branches in its first year of operation.

Table 2: Growth of Bank Islam from 1984 to 1992

	1984	1992
Total Asset	RM326 million	RM1.61 billion
Total Deposit	RM241 million	RM1.32 billion
Total Financing	RM161 million	RM1 billion
Profit/(loss) – before tax	(RM1.3million)	RM16.1 million
Number of branches	4	31

Since Bank Islam is under the supervision of the Central Bank, it has to comply with similar regulatory requirement as a conventional bank does in Malaysia. Effective from 1st January 1992, Bank Islam had to ensure that its minimum capital adequacy ratio was 8%. It also had to comply with other liquidity and statutory reserve requirement that is imposed on a conventional bank. The Government Investment Certificates (GIC) was a vital instrument to help Bank Islam meet its liquidity requirement. Due to Sharī'ah requirement, Bank Islam could not buy the Malaysian Government Securities (MGS), Malaysian Treasury Bill (MTB) or other interest bearing liquid instruments. GIC was introduced in July 1983 based on *qard al-ḥasan*, where by buying the instrument, Bank Islam was deemed to provide loan to the government. There will not be any predetermined return identified. However the government could at maturity give Bank Islam *hibah*. Nonetheless the GIC based on *qard* had limitation because Bank Islam could not trade it in the secondary market. To manage this issue, the Central Bank opened a window to allow Bank Islam to trade the GIC with the Central Bank. The price of the trade will be determined by the Central Bank (BNM, IIMM).

2.3 Phase Two - Competition

At the end of phase one, the regulators, the banking players and the customers were already familiar with the concept of Islamic banking. The Central Bank thus wanted to create more competition and stimulate market growth in the second phase (1993-2003). A number development occurred in the second stage. The main aim was to increase the number of players and establish the Islamic money market. In this section we will discuss the establishment of Islamic windows operation, Islamic money market, other important developments that took place and finally provide a snapshot of the size of the market at the end of the 2003.

a. Islamic Windows Operation

In order to increase the number of players in the Islamic banking market, the Central Bank had three options to consider; establish new Islamic banks, establish Islamic subsidiary of conventional banks or allow conventional banks to offer Islamic windows. As the first and second options would involve high cost, longer time and cause constrains in human resource, the Central Bank chose to pursue the third strategy. The

Interest Free Banking As Means of Inclusive Finance In India

third strategy was deemed as the best option to increase the number of players with the least time and least cost.

In order to apply for the scheme, the interested banks were required to submit paperwork to the Central Bank which elucidates among other the following information:

- i. branches that will offer the Islamic products;
- ii. type of Islamic deposits and financing that will be offered;
- iii. documents and agreements for each type of deposit and financing
- iv. infrastructure and human resource needs;
- v. method to segregate the Islamic fund from the conventional fund

Once approved by the Central Bank, the conventional banks had to set up an interest free banking unit (IBU) with a minimum fund dedicated solely for the use of the unit. The fund was known as Interest Free Banking Fund (IBF) and the minimum fund was RM100 million in 1993. In Malaysia, the regulators have from the beginning put in place regulations to ensure that funds raised using Islamic deposit is never channelled to the conventional operation. This is a critical issue as the “no leakage” policy has ensured that Islamic funds only chase Islamic assets in Malaysia. This in turn created a vibrant demand for the growth of the asset side of the Islamic banking market and other market segments in the Islamic financial system (Abdul Ghani & A. Hussain, 2009).

On 4th March 1993 the Central Bank introduced the first phase of Interest Free Banking Scheme (IFBS), where three largest commercial banks offered Islamic product within their conventional infrastructure. The banks involved were Malayan Banking Corporation, Bank Bumiputra Malaysia and United Malayan Banking Corporation. Then on 21st August 1993, the second phase of IFBS was launched where 10 more conventional banking institutions offered Islamic products. At the end of 1993, there were 21 financial institutions in Malaysia that offered IFBS (BNM, 1994).

b. Islamic Money Market

With more players in the market, the Central Bank also launched the Islamic Interbank Money Market (IIMM) in January 1994 to facilitate liquidity management for Islamic banks. The main instrument used was *muḍārabah*, where banks with surplus fund will provide capital to banks with deficit position. The tenure ranges from overnight to 12 months, while

the rate of return is based on one year gross profit rate. During the early stage of IIMM, the Central Bank regulated the profit sharing ratio according to the tenure as indicated below. When the market matured, the profit sharing ratio was left open to the negotiation of the parties.

Table 3: Regulated Profit Sharing Ratio during initial stage of *Mudārabah* interbank operation

Tenure	Profit Sharing Ratio between Surplus Bank (investor) and Deficit Bank (investee)
• One month or less	70:30
• Within 3 months	80:20
• More than 3 months	90:10

Source: BNM, 1994.

Table 4 shows other instruments that were available in the IIMM during the second phase of the development plan. Three out of four instruments were based on *bay' al-'inah* – a sale and buy back structure, while one instrument was based on *wadī'ah* or safe-keeping contract. In BNNN and GII, the aim is to allow the Islamic banks to invest their liquidity. If the Central Bank uses its own asset for this structure, it will first sell the underlying asset to the Islamic banks on spot basis and immediately buy back the asset on a deferred basis. The Central Bank will then issue the notes to evidence its obligation to pay the selling price to the investors. Note that GII is a replacement of GIC which was used in the first face as liquid security for Bank Islam to invest in. Since Malaysia allows *bay' al-'inah*, there was no issue in applying these concepts into the money market instruments. Malaysia also allows *bay' al-dayn* – the sale of debt structure which is not permissible according to Middle Eastern Sharī'ah scholars – thus allowing the GII to be traded in the secondary market.

In *bay' al-'inah* funding, the aim is to provide the Islamic banks with liquidity. Thus the Central Bank will first sell the asset to the Islamic bank on deferred basis. Then the bank will sell the asset back to the Central Bank on spot basis and gets the cash needed. Although the Malaysian market has been criticized for allowing *bay' al-'inah*, we can observe that this was just one of the instruments used. We will see in the next section that the Central Bank has the flexibility in allowing other instruments besides *bay' al-'inah* when needed.

Table 4: Islamic Money Market Instruments available in the second phase of the development of Islamic Banking market in Malaysia

Date	Instrument	Explanation
5 th August 1999	Bai al-Inah funding	Last resort funding by the Central Bank to cover deficit positions of Islamic banks
29 th Nov 2000	Bank Negara Negotiable Notes (BNNN)	Liquid securities issued by the Central Bank based on Bai al-Inah
15 th June 2001	Government Investment Issue (GII)	Liquid security issued by the government of Malaysia based on Bai al-Inah
15 th April 2002	Wadiah Acceptance	Islamic banking institutions place their surplus fund with the Central Bank based on the concept of Al- Wadiah (safekeeping). The Central Bank may pay hibah at its discretion.

Besides the Islamic interbank investment technique and Islamic money market instruments, the Central Bank also developed an Islamic cheque clearing system.¹ After about a year of the Islamic windows operation², beginning 3rd January 1994, the Central Bank segregated the cheque clearing system between the Islamic and conventional banking system. The Islamic cheque clearing system is conducted based on *muḍārabah*. At every midnight, the cheque clearing will be done automatically at the Central Bank. Any Islamic banks (window and full fledge) that faces deficit will be automatically balanced using funds from banks with surpluses based on *muḍārabah*. If the funds from the banking players are not sufficient to cover the deficit, the Central Bank would then cover the deficit based on *muḍārabah* as well. The profit sharing ratio was fixed at 70:30 between the investor and the investee bank (BNM, 1994). All these development in the Islamic money market was translated into an active Islamic interbank market. The volume of *muḍārabah* Interbank Investment (MII) alone jumped from RM0.5billion in 1994 to RM283.8 billion in 2003 (BNM, 2003).

c. Other developments in the second phase

Besides the establishment of Islamic windows operation and Islamic

¹ These three components (interbank investment technique, interbank instruments and cheque clearing system) were deemed vital for an efficient interbank money market

² The Islamic windows operation was first rolled on 4th March 1993 followed by the second phase on 21st August 1993.

money market, a number of developments occurred towards the end of phase two. This was in preparation for the final phase where the market will be liberalized. These developments are summarized in Table 5. It occurred in different areas; market development, strategic goal for the market, human capital development, legal infrastructure and regulatory framework updates. In an effort to increase more dedicated Islamic banks, a second full fledged Islamic bank, Bank Muamalat, was formed as a result of merger between Bank Bumiputra Malaysia Berhad (BBMB) and Bank of Commerce (BOC) in 1999.

Year 2001 witnessed the happening of two important events. First, the Central Bank laid down a strategic direction for the Malaysian financial market via the Financial Sector Master Plan. It was a 10 year development plan to build a resilient, efficient and competitive financial sector in Malaysia in an effort to liberalize the market. In the master plan, a target of 20% market share was set for the Islamic banking and takaful market. This target provided the market players a common goal to aim for. As the market was growing larger, there was a need to start thinking about human capital market development as well. Thus in February 2001 the Islamic Banking and Finance Institute Malaysia (IBFIM) was launched as an industry-owned research and training institute.

In year 2003 there were strong focus on the legal infrastructure and regulatory development. On the legal front, besides empowering a dedicated High Court to adjudicate all *muamalat* cases in the Commercial Division of High Court, the Central Bank was also exploring alternative dispute resolution mechanisms including arbitration and mediation for Islamic banking cases. In line with this, the Financial Mediation Bureau (FMB) was established as a single mediation centre for both banking and insurance, including Islamic banking and takaful. An important legal development in this phase also include the formation of the Law Review Committee in June 2003 by the Central Bank to review the existing law so recommendation can be made to the relevant authority in an effort to provide a conducive legal environment for Islamic banking and finance operation. The committee comprised of representatives from the Attorney General's Chambers, Ministry of Finance, Malaysian Bar Council, industry players and legal practitioners.

On the regulatory front, there were two important regulatory framework introduced. First, the Central Bank began reviewing the rate of

Interest Free Banking As Means of Inclusive Finance In India

return framework in an effort to standardise the methodology to calculate the distributable profits and rates of return to depositors in Islamic banks, particularly the *muḍārabah* deposit. Prior to this, different banks adopted different methods. The framework thus aimed to increase transparency in the market. The final rate of return framework was issued in August 2004 to the market. Second, Guidelines on the Specimen Reports and Financial Statements for Licensed Islamic Banks (GP8-i) was issued in August 2003. The guidelines dictated the minimum requirements that the Islamic banks need to disclose in their financial report. This provided users with lucid information on the performance Islamic banking operation in Malaysia.

Table 5: Other Developments in the Malaysian Islamic Banking Market Towards the End of Phase Two

Date	Area of Focus	Development
1999	Market development - players	Second full fledged Islamic Bank established – Bank Muamalat
2001	Strategic plan	Financial Sector Master Plan – target for growth in 10 years
	Human Capital Development	IBFIM was launched as one stop centre for training, education and research in Islamic finance
2003	Legal Infrastructure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dedicated high court to decide on Islamic banking cases 2. Financial Mediation Bureau (FMB) established as a single mediation centre for both banking and insurance, including Islamic banking and takaful 3. Law Review Committee to look at tax and stamp duty laws, company laws, land laws and procedural laws
	Regulatory framework	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Review Rate of Return Framework for <i>Muḍārabah</i> deposit 2. Issue guideline on reporting for Islamic banks (GP8-i)

d. Size of the market in phase two

At the end of phase 2 (i.e. year 2003), there were two full fledged Islamic banks and 31¹ conventional banks participating in the Islamic banking

¹ To be precise there were nine commercial banks, four foreign banks, seven finance companies, four merchant banks and seven discount houses that

scheme (IBS).¹ Table 6 shows the key statistic on the development of Islamic banking market at the end of phase two as compared to the earlier stage.

Table 6: Growth of Islamic banking market from 1984 to 1993²

	1984	1992	2003	% of banking system
Total Asset	RM326m	RM1.61 b	RM82 b	9.7%
Total Deposit	RM241m	RM1.32 b	RM60 b	10.4%
Total Financing	RM161m	RM1 b	RM49 b	10.3%
Number of branches	4	31	2217 ³	

We can observe that from the end of phase two (1992) to the end of phase three (2003), there has been tremendous growth in the total asset, total deposit, total financing of Islamic banks and the number of branches that offer Islamic products. The numbers attest to the success of the strategy pursued by the Central Bank. At the end of phase two, the Islamic banking market represented about 10% of the banking sector in Malaysia.

2.4 Phase Three - Liberalization

In phase three (2004 onward), the goal was to further liberalize the market. Table 7 shows the summary of development that happened in the third phase. Year 2004 witnessed a number of important developments that covers market development, Shari'ah governance and tax framework in Malaysia. In an effort to further strengthen and liberalize the market, the Central Bank implemented two major steps. First, it encouraged the Islamic windows to set up Islamic subsidiaries that were licensed similar to full-fledged Islamic bank. RHB Islamic was the first banking group that took up the challenge. Compared to Islamic window structure, a subsidiary shows the commitment that the institution has to become a long term player in the market. To set up the subsidiary, the institutions needed RM50

participated in the Islamic Banking Scheme. (BNM, 2003)

¹ Starting December 1998, the term Interest Free Banking Scheme (IFBS) was replaced with Islamic Banking Scheme (IBS). Source: (Ahmad Mokhtar & Al-Habshi, 2007)

² The 1984 and 1992 data are from Bank Islam Annual report while the 2003 data is from the Central Bank Annual report

³ 152 full-fledged Islamic banking branches and 2,065 Islamic banking counters (under Islamic window)

Interest Free Banking As Means of Inclusive Finance In India

million minimum capital and its own management team including board of directors and a dedicated CEO. The Central Bank also allowed 49% foreign shareholding in the Islamic subsidiaries.

Table 7: Developments in the Malaysian Islamic Banking Market in Phase Three

Date	Area of Focus	Development
2004	Market Development - players	1. Recommend Islamic window to convert into Islamic subsidiaries 2. Grant license to three foreign Islamic bank
	Shari'ah Governance	Guideline on Governance of Shari'ah Committee
	Tax Neutrality	An equitable tax treatment of Islamic banking transactions vis-à-vis similar conventional banking transactions was announced in 2005 Budget
2006	Islamic Money Market	Sukuk Ijarah issuance by the Central Bank
	Human Capital Development	INCEIF was established to offer professional certificate and post graduate studies in Islamic Finance
	Market Development	MIFC was established to encourage foreign currency business in Malaysia
2007	Islamic Money Market	Commodity Murabahah Program by the Central Bank
2008	Human Capital Development	ISRA was established to conduct research on applied Shari'ah issues
2009	Islamic Money Market	Suq Al-Sila' – a commodity trading platform for liquidity management purposes

Source: Various BNM's Annual Report

Second, the Central Bank brought forward the liberalization exercise of the Islamic banking sector when it issued three (3) foreign Islamic bank licenses to Islamic banks from the Middle East. Kuwait Finance House (Malaysia) was the first foreign Islamic bank to start operation in Malaysia in February 2006. This was followed by Al-Rajhi – a Saudi based Islamic bank, in October 2006 and finally by Asian Finance Bank in January 2007. Besides bringing new products and approach to the Malaysian market, the entrance of these Islamic banks also meant that the Central Bank was ready to explore the regulatory and supervisory guidance needed for the different business models adopted by these banks.

Besides market development, the Central Bank also strengthened the Shari'ah Governance framework in 2004 with the issuance of Guidelines on Governance of Shari'ah Committee for Islamic Financial Institutions. Prior to this guideline, various Shari'ah bodies were governed under

separate legal framework and one Shari'ah scholar can sit on various Shari'ah boards. The Central Bank had already established the National Shari'ah Advisory Council (NSAC) on 1st May 1997. However all other Shari'ah committees (banking, takaful, NBF) operated independently from the NSAC. To manage this, in 2003, the Central Bank amended the Central Bank Act to enhance the role of NSAC. With the amendment, the NSAC was the sole authoritative body regarding Shari'ah matters in Islamic banking and finance. This was seen as an important move to eliminate any confusion among public.

In Malaysia, the appointment of Shari'ah scholars must be approved by the Central Bank. The Guideline issued in 2004 clarified the role and responsibilities of the Shari'ah Board, the appointment procedures and qualifying criteria of Shari'ah advisors. The guideline also limited the number of Shari'ah board that a Shari'ah advisor can sit on. A scholar is only allowed to sit as a Shari'ah Committee member of an Islamic financial institution and a Shari'ah Committee member of another Islamic financial institution of a different industry. For example, a Shari'ah scholar may advise an Islamic bank and at the same time becomes the Shari'ah advisor for a takaful operator or other industries. (Mokhtar, 2009)

The Malaysian Government continued to show its support for the industry when it announced the tax neutrality policy for Islamic banking and finance in the 2005 Budget. Under the tax neutrality framework, the Inland Revenue Board (IRB) will exempt additional stamp duty and tax payment that is required to fulfil Shari'ah requirement. The Income Tax Act 1967, Real Property Gains Tax Act 1976 and Stamp Act 1949 required amendment in order to provide the tax neutrality (BNM Annual Report, 2004).

For subsequent development in the third phase, we can observe a common trend. The Central Bank emphasized on two main areas – human capital development and enhancement of Islamic money market. Before going deeper into these two areas, let us first discuss a very important market development that took place in 2006. Since Malaysia has strengthened its domestic market in the second phase, it was now ready to expand its wing into the international financial arena. In line with this aim, Malaysia launched an initiative known as the Malaysia International Islamic Financial Centre (MIFC) in August 2006 to facilitate the transformation of Malaysia into an international hub for Islamic finance.

MIFC focuses on three main areas – International Islamic Banking & Takaful, Sukuk and Islamic fund & wealth management. Simply put, the focus of MIFC is to develop the foreign currency business in these areas. With MIFC initiative, the Central Bank provided licenses for either existing Islamic financial institutions or new Islamic financial institutions to conduct Islamic banking business in foreign currency.

Now let's focus on the two main trends of development in the third phase. First, let's discuss efforts put in place for human capital development. As a continuous effort to enhance human resource for the industry, in 2006, the Central Bank established the International Center for Education in Islamic Finance (INCEIF) which provided professional qualification and post graduate studies. Two years later (2008), the Central Bank established the International Shariah Research Academy for Islamic Finance (ISRA) which was mandated among others to conduct applied research in Shari'ah issues to facilitate product development.

The other trend of development in the third phase was related to the enrichment of Islamic money market. The Central Bank issued its inaugural *Sukuk Ijarah* in February 2006 and launched the Commodity *murābahah* deposit in 2008 to further develop the Malaysian Islamic money market.¹ If we recall, in the second phase, most of the money market instruments were based on *bay' al-īnah* which is not acceptable to Middle Eastern institutions. With the entry of three foreign Islamic banks in the third phase, the Central Bank considered offering alternative money market instruments to help the foreign Islamic banks manage their liquidity. This attests to the flexibility that the Malaysian market has to accommodate different needs of different market players. As the demand for commodity *murābahah* was continuously increasing, the Central Bank, the Securities Commission and Bursa Malaysia under the leadership of MIFC worked together to launch Bursa Suq Al-Sila' in August 2009. This is an electronic commodity trading platform based on commodity *murābahah* (tawarruq) structure at Bursa Malaysia specifically dedicated for Islamic liquidity management. The Islamic banks can use this platform for a broad variety of products ranging from deposit, financing, hedging instruments and interbank placements.

¹ Please refer to Appendix 1 for an explanation of how the *Sukuk Ijarah* and Commodity *Murabahah* deposit works

As at November 2009, the Islamic banking industry has grown to witness the establishment of 36 Islamic financial institutions holding a market share of about 19% of total banking asset in Malaysia. Namely there are seventeen (17) Islamic banks (inclusive of Islamic subsidiaries of conventional banks), ten (10) Islamic windows, six (6) development finance institutes (DFIs) and three (3) international Islamic banks. Figure 2 shows the list of players in the Islamic banking sector in Malaysia.

3. CURRENT STATE OF ISLAMIC BANKING IN INDIA

India has the third largest Muslim population in the world (156 million Muslims), just behind Indonesia (207 million) and Pakistan (171 million).¹ Nonetheless, the growth of Islamic finance is still at a very nascent stage. According to the Banker’s survey, India only owns 0.1% market share in the Shari’ah compliant asset in the non-MENA region (Timewell & DiVanna, 2009).

Figure 2: Non-MENA market share of Shari’ah compliant asset, 2009

The legal framework in India does not explicitly prohibit Islamic banking activities however the following provisions in the Indian banking law has

¹ Source: CIA Factbook in (Invest East, n.d)

Interest Free Banking As Means of Inclusive Finance In India

prevented the establishment of Islamic banks in the country (Islahi, 1997; KFH Research, 2009; Nisar & Aziz, 2004):

- i. Section 5(b) and 5(c) of the Banking Regulation Act 1949 prohibit the banks from investing on a profit-and-loss sharing basis
- ii. Section 8 of the Banking Regulation Act 1949 reads: “No banking company shall directly or indirectly deal in buying or selling or bartering of goods...”
- iii. Section 9 of the Banking Regulation Act 1949 prohibits banks from using any sort of immovable property apart from private use
- iv. Section 21 of the Banking Regulation Act 1949 requires payment of interest.

If we analyze the restrictions above it clashes head on with how an Islamic bank operates. Due to this impediment, the current Islamic finance activities in India have focused on the non-banking financial institutions (NBFI) sector particularly the non-banking financial companies (NBFC) and mutual funds. A major difference between banks and NBFCs in India is the ability of the former to source for demand deposits (deposits payable immediately on demand or within a short period of time like savings and current accounts). In addition, NBFCs are not a part of the payment and settlement system, thus they cannot issue cheques. Last but not least, NBFC customers' deposits are not covered by deposit insurance (RBI, 2007).

These differences then provide banks with an added advantage because it can tap into a wide source of deposit. Most retail depositors prefer the ability to withdraw money when needed and the deposit insurance protection gives them a sense of security. Businesses on the other hand would require cheques for payment purposes. Since NBFCs don't have these advantages, the pool of deposits that they can tap into would be limited which then limits the growth on their asset side.

Khan (2007) made an excellent observation of the challenges that an Islamic bank would face in India (if it were regulated under the current banking law). First and foremost banks need to invest in liquid securities to fulfil their cash reserve requirement (CRR) and statutory liquidity ratio (SLR). Currently the central government securities and other approved securities pay interest. Without this cash reserves and SLR Islamic banks then cannot become members of settlement/clearing house. The second

challenge that he highlighted was the fact that the Central Bank cannot act as the lender of last resort because again the operation is interest based. Finally, the Islamic banks would also face challenges to interact with conventional banks in the interbank market when they face liquidity squeezes.

The factors highlighted by (Khan, 2007) are crucial since there was evidence of Islamic NBFCs' failure in India due to liquidity constraints. (Nisar & Aziz, 2004) elucidated that Barkat Investment Group (BIG), a prominent Islamic NBFC that was established in 1983, was forced to close shop in May 2000 due to liquidity constraints. They noted that due to limited business options, BIG invested heavily in stock and real estate for their operation. When the stock market and real estate went tumbling down in year 1997-98, BIG incurred large losses (about 25%). It had to divest its high performing shares at depressed prices because it did not have other instruments to manage its liquidity constraint.

Even with all these impediments in place, the interest to introduce Islamic banking in India did not wear out. On 27th January 2010, the Deputy Speaker of the Rajya Sabha and senior Congress leader, K Rahman Khan, proposed to the Prime Minister the idea of establishing a Shari'ah compliant bank which he terms as Participatory Banking. A committee headed by the Cabinet Secretary K. M. Chandrasekhar was then asked to submit a report to the Prime Minister about the issue (ANI, 2010). However, on 5th March 2010, the Indian government decided to put on hold the recommendation to introduce Islamic banks in India (IAN, 2010).

In the next section, we will draw lessons from the Malaysian experience and aim to provide some recommendations to address the challenges highlighted by Khan, 2007. We hope that the Malaysian experience could then serve as a blue print to introduce Islamic banking in India.

4. LEARNING FROM THE MALAYSIAN EXPERIENCE

From our analysis in section two, we observe that Malaysia have successfully experimented a strategy which can be adapted for the Indian market. In sum, there are 5 ingredients that Malaysia has adopted in the process of successfully growing its Islamic banking market; top-down

approach, no leakage policy, Shari'ah regulation, responsive legal framework and human resources development.

In the first phase of development, Malaysia aimed to increase the number of products with just one full fledged bank. This allowed the regulator to evaluate the viability of a new banking model in the banking system. When the sole Islamic bank has developed large number of products, the aim in the second phase was to increase the number of players in the market. This was done via the establishment of Islamic windows because this was the option that was most effective to obtain large number of players within the shortest time period and least cost. When there were large numbers of players, the Central Bank then developed the Islamic money market to facilitate the liquidity management of these banks. This top down approach and strategic planning is the first ingredient for Malaysia's success.

Complementing this strategic plan, Malaysia practices a no-leakage policy which then forces deposits raised in the Islamic banks to be applied only towards Shari'ah compliant assets. This would then allow the supply and demand forces to naturally develop the market. The third important ingredient for success is regulated Shari'ah management in Malaysia. Having a centralized Shari'ah advisory council provides uniformity of Shari'ah view. In addition, limiting the number of Shari'ah board that an individual can advise has pushed the Malaysian Islamic banking industry to develop a wide pool of Shari'ah advisors. Many local Islamic banks recruited new and young scholars into their Shari'ah board and provided them with various training and exposure. This means that the Shari'ah regulation has indirectly managed the issue of limited number of Shari'ah scholars in market (Laldin, 2008).

In order to facilitate Islamic finance transaction, tax neutrality is a must. Malaysia started this process back in 2004 and has been continuously reviewing the legal and tax framework to provide level playing field between Islamic and conventional finance. This is what we call responsive legal framework. Last but not least, the Malaysian government has invested in developing human capital through not only public universities in Malaysia, but also by establishing institutions like IBFIM, INCEIF and ISRA. Human development is a crucial factor as this would provide constant flow of workforce for the development of the industry.

Drawing lessons from the Malaysian experience, India can start the experiment with an Islamic window first. Currently, the institutions that

offer Islamic finance in India fall under the category of non-banking financial companies (NBFC). We suggest that the banking sector is the most suitable sector to enhance the growth of the Indian Islamic banking market as banks are able to mobilize wider sources of deposits compared to NBFCs. Furthermore, if we look into the Indian banking law, there are restriction for banks to deal in profit and loss sharing arrangement, trading of goods and investment in immovable property. All these activities are required for an Islamic bank to conduct its operation.

If India is not yet ready to come up with a separate Islamic banking act, it can always explore the possibility of making a staggered review of the banking law to provide exemptions to certain regulated segments to allow Islamic banking operation. This means that the Reserve Bank of India can first allow the window to conduct certain regulated activities (*murābahah* or *'ijārah* for example). Some tax neutrality policy changes (again on a limited scope) must also take place. Based on the performance and viability of this exempted operation model, RBI can then review other laws in stages. The staggered approach would allow both the Islamic window and RBI to gain experience and make the necessary adjustment to grow the market.

Khan (2007) noted that liquidity management would be a challenge for Islamic banks in India. For the early stage (i.e. when there is only one Islamic window), the RBI only need to put in place one liquidity management instrument. The best option would be to have the Government or the Central Bank issuing short term securities that fulfils Shari'ah requirement. Depending on the Shari'ah view that India is going to adopt, it can use either commodity *murābahah* or *'ijārah* as the underlying Shari'ah principle for these instruments.

Commodity *murābahah* would be the easiest to start with because the instrument can also be used as a device for the lender of last resort operation.¹ However the Islamic window may face issues for trading the instrument in secondary market due to Shari'ah ruling on trading of debt (*bay' al-dayn*). However, for short term instrument, this would be a feasible mechanism to start with. We provide explanation of the commodity *murābahah* programme that was adopted by the Central Bank

¹ Although this product may not be the best solution from Shariah perspective, it would give India a chance to explore the opportunities that Islamic banking and finance has to offer.

of Malaysia in Appendix 1. Besides commodity *murābahah*, RBI can also explore an *ijārah* instrument. However it would depend on the willingness of RBI to inject some assets to facilitate the structure. As for liquidity placement with the central bank, RBI can provide *wadī'ah* placement option for the Islamic window. Depending on the success of the first experiment, RBI can then make more changes and allow more players to set up windows. When there are enough players in the market, then it would be worth considering the establishment of an Islamic money market and the components to make it a success.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The benefits that Islamic finance can bring are numerous. It will not only serve the Muslim population but will also benefit the non-Muslims as well. The Malaysian market has again provided evidence that Islamic banking products attract the interest of Muslims and non-Muslim. The deputy president of Maybank, Agil Natt, was quoted as saying that 45% of Maybank's Islamic banking customers are non-Muslim (A. & Muto, n.d). In a more recent news (December 2008), OCBC Al-Amin's CEO, Syed Abdull Aziz Syed Kechik said that 50% of the Islamic banking customer of OCBC are non-Muslims (Reuters, 2008).

Islamic banking can truly be inclusive finance in India if there are effort for continuous education and awareness increasing activities. Among efforts that Malaysia has put in place include hosting the production of 11 episode documentary programme about the development of the Islamic financial system in Malaysia and the production of information booklets about Islamic banking. Last but not least, as the use of the word "Islamic" may cause negative perception among non-Muslims in India, the market can simply be given other names like what Kuwait Finance House, Al-Rajhi and Asian Finance Bank has done for example.

In conclusion, we hope that the Malaysian experience will provide some guidance and knowledge sharing for RBI to explore the opportunity in the Islamic banking market. If China is receptive to this idea, then India would not lose out if it provides some avenue to adapt the ingredients that has brought success in Malaysia according to India's need.

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Interest Free Banking As Means of Inclusive Finance In India

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Appendix 1: Money Market Instruments based on globally accepted standards

1. Sukuk Bank Negara Malaysia Ijarah (SBNMI)

This *Sukuk* is based on the sale and lease back concept, a structure that is widely used in the Middle East. For the purpose of issuing the *Sukuk*, a special purpose vehicle, BNM *Sukuk* Berhad was established. The SPV will issue the *Sukuk* and use the proceeds from the issuance to purchase Bank Negara Malaysia's assets. The assets will then be leased to the Central Bank. The rental collected will be distributed to investors as a return on a semi-annual basis. At maturity (the end of the lease tenure), the SPV will then sell the assets back to the Central Bank at a predetermined price. The inaugural issuance of this *Sukuk* took place on 16 February 2006 with an issue size of RM400 million. This *Sukuk* is issued on a regular basis with subsequent issues ranging from RM100 million to RM200 million.

2. Commodity Murabaha Programme (BNM, 2007)

The Central Bank first offered the Commodity *Murabahah* on 14th March 2007 to support the liquidity management operation of especially foreign Islamic bank in Malaysia. It is a cash deposit product based on commodity *Murabahah* (Tawarruq). The diagram below illustrates how the cash deposit works. The underlying asset used was crude palm oil (CPO).

